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GrInShield newsletter

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I Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences – National Institute of the Republic of Serbia

Founded in 1948, the Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences has become a major scientific institution in Serbia, known for its multidisciplinary research. Nowadays, it covers fields like physics, chemistry, biology, energy, and environmental protection. Thanks to its interdisciplinary approach, the institute is well-equipped to address key research priorities set at the national level, including new materials and nanosciences, energy, biomedicine, and environmental protection. Since its establishment, more than 750 scientists have obtained their doctoral degrees at the Vinča Institute.

Some of its main laboratories include the Laboratory for Physics, Laboratory for Nuclear Physics, Laboratory for Physical Chemistry, Laboratory for Molecular Biology and Endocrinology, and Laboratory for Radiation Chemistry and Physics, among others. The institute is a leader in high-tech fields, particularly in areas such as ionizing radiation protection, production and distribution of radiopharmaceuticals, testing and verification of energy efficiency measures in thermal power plants, equipment calibration, and product testing.

As the lead institution in the **GrInShield** project, the Vinča Institute is developing advanced graphene oxide (GO)-based materials to protect against electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding. Supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe program, this project unites experts across Europe in nanomaterials, polymers, and electronics to create innovative EMI shielding solutions. Enhancing knowledge of the Vinča Institute administration is achieved through collaboration and transfer of best practices with the Institute of Electronics, Microelectronics and Nanotechnology (IEMN-CNRS) - FRA and Fakulteta za tehnologijo polimerov (FTPO)- SI offices for project implementation.

II GrInShield Trainings and Workshops ***Workshop at IEMN, Lille, France***

A key goal of the **GrInShield** project is to support young researchers in gaining knowledge and hands-on skills by working with top scientific institutions in the EU. In line with this, the GrInShield team organized a workshop on 14-15th May 2024 at the **Institute of Electronics, Microelectronics, and Nanotechnology (IEMN)** focused on "**Microwave Modelling & Characterization; Dielectric & Shielding Materials**". Over two days, participants attended technical sessions and were engaged in discussions with experts.

GrInShield Summer School in Slovenia

From June 26-28th 2024, the **second GrInShield Summer School**, entitled "**Polymer Technology – Processing and Manufacturing**", was held in Slovenj Gradec at the **Faculty of Polymer Technology (FTPO)**. The school brought a comprehensive introduction to the key concepts of polymer processing, 3D printing, and rheology, with hands-on workshops and interactive sessions. Experts in the field led practical demonstrations, providing valuable knowledge on the latest trends and technologies in polymer manufacturing. This engaging program encouraged collaboration and allowed participants to deepen their understanding of polymer science.

GrInShield's Workshop

Bringing together top experts and researchers from across Europe, the **GrInShield Workshop „Synthesis of carbon-based nanomaterials, green approaches in their productions, and gamma irradiation as a tool for their modification“**, held from July 16th to 18th, 2024, highlighted the latest advancements in the study of carbon-based nanomaterials. The first day opened with a welcome speech from Dr. Dragana Marinković and an overview of the **GrInShield** project's progress by coordinator Svetlana Jovanović. Special guests, including Vesna Adamović and François-Xavier Kowandy from the Institut français de Serbie, joined the opening ceremony. The day was filled with insightful talks from **GrInShield** team members, Dr. Dejan Kepić, Dr. Jovana Prekodravac, and Dr. Marija Radoičić, who shared their latest research on carbon nanomaterials. GrInShield team members from CNRS, Dr. Kamel Haddadi and Dr. Christophe Loyez demonstrated graphene's potential in sensor applications. The second day of the workshop focused on life cycle assessment, with Prof. Dr. Gruescu Ion Cosmin from the University of Lille leading a session on sustainable material development. On the final day, the workshop explored the practical applications of carbon-based nanomaterials in fields such as cytotoxicity, antibacterial properties, and acoustic technology. Dr. Marija Mojsin and Prof. Dr. Vladimir Jurišić presented research on evaluating cytotoxicity, while Dr. Ana Dobrota discussed the latest findings on single-atom catalysts. The day concluded with sessions on the role of graphene membranes in acoustic technology and the study of electromagnetic fields.

European Microwave Week 2024

GrInShield's IEMN team leader, Dr. Kamel Haddadi, together with François Piquemal and Peter Burke, organized a specialized workshop on **Microwave Nanoscale Modelling and Characterization** on September 23rd, 2024, as part of **European Microwave Week 2024**, the second-largest microwave event in the world! The workshop featured remarkable presentations by experts and project coordinator Dr. Svetlana Jovanović, who shed light on the challenges of characterizing graphene-based composites within the **GrInShield** project.

On-site Training at IEMN

The "**Hands-on Training for Investigating Electrical and Shielding Properties of Materials**" took place from October 28th to 30th, 2024, at the **CNRS-IEMN** in Lille, France. Members of the VINCA team participated in practical training focused on conducting reliable and repeatable measurements of shielding efficiency while studying various carbon-based composites.

III GrInShield Team at Conferences and events

The **GrInShield** team has actively participated in several conferences worldwide, sharing their latest research on carbon-based nanomaterials and electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding.

At the **22nd Iranian Chemistry Congress** in Tehran, Dr. Miroslav Huskic gave two lectures. On May 13th, he discussed the "**Synthesis and characterization of graphene oxide-silver nanowires composites for EMI shielding**", highlighting factors that affect the GO yield and thermal stability differences. The next day, he presented "**Carbon-based polymer composites for EMI shielding**", emphasizing the role of carbon-based nanomaterials in developing effective shielding materials.

At the **International Conference on Manipulation, Automation, and Robotics at Small Scales (MARSS 2024)** in Delft, the **GrInShield** coordinator Dr. Svetlana Jovanović chaired a special session on "**New nanomaterials for electromagnetic interference shielding**". Dr. Dejan Kepić, Dr. Marija Radoičić, and Prof. Dr. Kamel Haddadi shared recent findings on nanomaterial-based shielding solutions.

On June 3rd, 2024, Dr. Jovana Prekodravac presented **GrInShield's** goals and latest results at the **Institute of Physical Chemistry** in Warsaw, Poland. Her lecture highlighted the diverse applications of carbon-based nanomaterials, including water purification, antibacterial properties, and electromagnetic shielding. Prof. Dr. Juan Carlos Colmenares hosted this meeting. At **NanoTech Poland 2024** in Poznań, Dr. Prekodravac presented her work on "**GO-AgNWs Free-Standing Composite Films for Microwave Electromagnetic Interference Shielding**", emphasizing how material properties impact shielding performance up to 18 GHz.

Graphene 2024, the largest European conference for graphene and 2D materials, brought together over 500 participants to share ideas and discuss new developments. Dr. Dejan Kepić presented his research on the EMI shielding efficiency of graphene composites with silver nanoparticles treated with low-dose gamma irradiation. The conference is held from June 25th to 28th in Madrid.

On August 22nd, Dr. Dragana Marinković presented **GrInShield**'s progress at the **14th International Conference on Ceramic Materials** in Budapest, Hungary. Her talk focused on using gamma irradiation to modify carbon-based materials and their potential for electromagnetic shielding.

During Slovenski kemijski dnevi 2024, from September 18th to 20th in Portorož, Slovenia, master's student Tadej Slatinek presented his results from the **GrInShield** project on "**Thermal Stability of Graphene Oxide**".

GrInShield team member Dr. Duška Kleut presented her lecture, "**Key factors in electromagnetic interference shielding by graphene-based composites**", at the **8th IEEE Symposium on Wireless Technology & Applications (ISWTA 2024)** in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.

At the **International Symposium on Analytical and Environmental Problems (ISAEP 2024)** in Szeged, Hungary, Dr. Kleut presented a poster titled "**Quince Biowaste for Production of Graphene-based Nanomaterials used for Electromagnetic Shielding**" on October 8th, 2024.

IV Stakeholder Collaboration

One of the key objectives of the GrInShield project is to strengthen partnerships between the scientific and business sectors. In this regard, we are pleased to announce 4 new additions to our stakeholder network: **the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Serbia (CCIS), Dirigent Acoustics, the Ministry of Environmental Protection of the Republic of Serbia, and Institute Nicola Tesla - the Electromagnetic field testing laboratory.** We are grateful for their support and recognition of the project's potential and look forward to collaborating with them.

V Public Engagement and Media Appearances

In September 2024, the **GrInShield** team participated in several key events to share their research and achievements. During a **radio interview**, they provided updates on the project's progress and its contributions to EMI shielding research. On September 20th, the team also presented their work at the **Vinca Open Door** and on September 27th at **European Researchers' Night** at the House of Europe in Belgrade, attended by EU Ambassador H.E.

VI Career Promotion within GrInShield

Andjela Stefanović, a member of the **GrInShield** project at the Vinča Institute, has been promoted to Research Assistant, marking an important milestone in her career within the project. In addition, Ana Pantić successfully defended her Master's thesis on EMI shielding at the Faculty of Physics, University of Belgrade, demonstrating her commitment to advancing research in this crucial area.

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Here you can find important news and the biggest achievements of the project. Make sure to subscribe to GrInShield's profiles so you don't miss any of our upcoming events. Also, we launched a website - grinshield.eu - where you can find all the relevant data about the project.

